

NON-INVASIVE TECHNIQUES FOR CHARACTERIZING THE PIGMENTS APPLIED ON WALL HOUSES FROM ROMAN APULUM (ROMANIA)

DUMITRITA DANIELA FILIP^{1,2}, MIHAI GLIGOR¹, ILIE ALEXANDRU LASCU²,
IOAN ALIN BUCURICA^{3,*}, CRISTIANA RADULESCU^{4,5,6,*},
RALUCA MARIA STIRBESCU³, IOANA DANIELA DULAMA^{3,*}

¹“1 Decembrie 1918” University of Alba Iulia, 510009 Alba Iulia, Romania
E-mail: *mihai.gligor@uab.ro; dumitruta.filip@yahoo.com*

²National Museum of Union Alba Iulia, 510010 Alba Iulia, Romania
E-mail: *lascuia@yahoo.com*

³Institute of Multidisciplinary Research for Science and Technology, Valahia University
of Targoviste, 130004 Targoviste, Romania

E-mail: *bucurica_alin@icstm.ro; stirbescu.raluca@icstm.ro; dulama.ioana@icstm.ro*

⁴Department of Sciences and Arts, Valahia University of Targoviste, 130004 Targoviste, Romania
E-mail: *radulescucristiana@yahoo.com*

⁵Doctoral School Chemical Engineering and Biotechnology, National University for Science
and Technology Politehnica of Bucharest, 060042 Bucharest, Romania

⁶Academy of Romanian Scientists, 050044 Bucharest, Romania

* Corresponding author, E-mail: *radulescucristiana@yahoo.com*

Received December 10, 2024

Abstract. In the past 136 years, numerous archaeological finds have enriched the history of Roman Apulum and Roman Province Dacia with new data. Various pieces were described and analyzed from a stylistic point of view, but they were not investigated in terms of non-invasive analytical techniques to elucidate the painting techniques and the materials used. In this context, this study aims to identify and characterize the pigments used by Roman painters/craftsmen in decorating houses using Apulum and the painting technique. To achieve this goal, fragments of Roman wall paintings recently discovered in three different archaeological excavations from the ancient Roman Apulum were selected and studied using non-invasive analytical techniques (optical microscopy and vibrational spectroscopy). They have various colors and shades, such as red, green, blue, white, yellow, and admixtures. To establish the potential materials used for wall painting, the samples were analyzed by micro-Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy.

Key words: Roman wall painting, pigment, Apulum, optical microscopy, micro-FTIR.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.59277/RomRepPhys.2025.77.803>

1. INTRODUCTION

The current research regarding archaeometric studies on the wall paintings of the Roman era is very advanced in other countries – former territories of the

Roman Empire [1–6]. The stage of stylistic analysis and description of the painted subjects has long passed, and a new stage that reveals some "secrets" or technical peculiarities was beginning. The pigments, the composition of the plasters [6] and mortars [5], and the provenance of the materials were identified [1]. Since the Fribourg conference in 1996, which highlighted Roman wall paintings from Pannonia [7], Israel [8, 9], Corinth [10], Cyprus [11], France [12], Pompeii and Rome [13], Spain [14], including tools and materials used by Roman painters [15], up to now (*i.e.*, Ruth Sidall's work on investigation techniques and pigments identified in wall painting [16] and Salvadori and Sbrolli [17] studied the Roman paintings from the period of the Republic and the Empire and others), important steps and analysis of Roman wall painting have been carried out to identify the chemical composition of the materials used. On the territory of the former Roman Dacia province, although numerous wall painting fragments have been discovered, they have not been studied from a technical point of view. Thus, at this moment there are extremely few studies on this topic: the study of wall painting fragments from Rapoltu Mare [18], Ulpia Traiana Sarmizegetusa [19], and Alburnus Maior (Roşia Montana) [20]. In the archaeological campaigns carried out in the last decades, numerous fragments of wall painting from the Roman Dacia were discovered and retrieved from Apulum (Alba Iulia City), most of them excavated within private buildings/houses, which were not exploited from the perspective of archaeometric investigations. This paper thus opens a new path in the study of the technique and the materials employed in the wall painting from Apulum, by carrying out archaeometric analysis.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. ARCHAEOLOGICAL CONTEXT

Dacia became a Roman province during Emperor Trajan's rule (after the Roman conquest of AD 106) and was reorganized (Fig. 1, [21]) by the next emperor, Hadrian, who decided to divide it into three, *i.e.*, Dacia Porolissensis, Dacia Superior, and Dacia Inferior, ruled by a Governor, who had his headquarter in Apulum (Alba Iulia City). After AD 168–169 – the administrative reform of Emperor Marcus Aurelius, Apulum became the political and military capital of the Roman province – Dacia, an important urban center of the Empire. Thus, the civil settlement from Apulum developed into a complex urban center that included the *canabae legionis XIII Geminae*, which became a municipium – *Municipium Septimium Apulense* (Apulum II) in AD 197 and the *colonia Aurelia Apulense* (Apulum I).

The samples investigated in this study are from rescue excavations (coded from S1 to S3) located inside the ancient Roman Apulum II (Fig. 2, [22]), part of

the site *Municipium Septimium Apulense* (the *Canabae legionis XIII Geminae*). They are wall paintings that once decorated the Roman houses from Apulum, fallen into fragments due to the wall's collapse.

Fig. 1 – Map of Roman Dacia after the administrative re-organization of Emperor Hadrian [21].

Fig. 2 – General map of Apulum (left side) [22] with S1, S2, and S3; Google Earth capture (right side) highlighting the S1, S2, and S3 archaeological excavations.

The APL-1 to APL-6 samples (Fig. 3) representing wall painting fragments discovered in the room located in the central-western part of the trench was excavated from S1 (Fig. 2), located at 360 m East from the Roman legionary fort of *Legio XIII Gemina*, 200 m North from Governors' Palace (*Pretorium consularis*), and 90 m from the excavations undertaken in 1962 by Berciu and Popa [23]. The current address of the site location is 5B Basarabiei Street. Rescue excavations were undertaken between 2021 and 2022 on a surface of 269.29 m².

The APL-7 to APL-12 samples consisting of wall painting fragments and red painted floor fragments (Fig. 4) were collected from the S2 site (Fig. 2), located to the Western part of the Roman necropolis on Dealul Furcilor-Podei, to the South-East of *castra Legionis XIII Geminae*, and South-West from the Governors' Palace – excavations of Cserni, Berciu, and Bolindeț [24]. The current address of the site location is 15A Dimitrie Cantemir Street. The archaeological excavation was undertaken in 2019 on a surface of 140 m², divided into three squares tagged from North to South with A, B, and C.

The samples APL-13 to APL-15 (Figs. 2, 5) were collected from the third site (*i.e.*, S3), located to the Western limit of the *canabae legionis*, at 300 m from the *castra legionis XIII Geminae*. The current address of the site location is 20C Aurel Vlaicu Street. The archaeological excavation was carried out at the end of 2023 on 225 m² surface. Eleven archaeological complexes outlined by tranches of dismantled walls were discovered. The samples are part of a dismantled wall coded Z1.

Fig. 3 – Samples APL-1 to APL-6 collected from S1 site.

Fig. 4 – Samples APL-7 to APL-12 collected from S2 site, square C.

Fig. 5 – Samples APL-13 to APL-15 collected from S3 site.

2.2. ANALYTICAL TECHNIQUES

Wall paintings were preliminary observed by a Stemi 2000-C stereo microscope, equipped with an external cold light 50 W (CL4500 LED); images were collected by an Axiocam 105 digital video camera (Zeiss, Germany) controlled by the ZEN software. Molecular information related to analyzed samples was gained through micro-Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (micro-FTIR) for organic/inorganic

compounds, using a Vertex 80 spectrometer coupled with a high-resolution infrared microscope, Hyperion 3000 (Bruker, Germany); spectra acquisition and identification of functional groups were achieved through the internal library and Opus v8 software.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study utilized optical microscopy for a better understanding of the technique used for pigments applied on the Roman walls and the finesse of the execution, aspects which couldn't be established just visually on a macro scale. Therefore, was observed that between the plaster and the paint (pigment mixed with limestone – CaCO_3) was applied a white layer for all studied samples (*e.g.*, APL-1, Fig. 6a), except made by sample APL-9.

In the case of the APL-9 sample, a black pigment can be observed instead (Fig. 6b). After carefully studying all the samples, it is worth noting that to obtain different shades of the same pigment, successive layers of different colors were used. Thus, in the case of samples APL-7 and APL-10, to get a shade of lighter red, three successive layers of white, yellow, and red were used (Fig. 6c–d). The same technique was applied to green (APL-11, Fig. 6e) or gray (APL-2, Fig. 6f) pigments: three successive layers of white-yellow-green and white-yellow-grey/black, respectively.

Fig. 6 – Optical microscopy images: a) APL-1; b) APL-9; c) APL-7; d) APL-10; e) APL-11; f) APL-2.

Micro-FTIR spectroscopy, a valuable non-invasive tool, was used to identify the inorganic pigments containing oxides and sulfides frequently included in ancient wall paintings. Based on the wavelength values, the fingerprint peaks and vibrational bands' assignment in the mid-infrared spectral range ($4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$), are shown in Table 1 for all analyzed samples. First, the presence of calcite-type carbonates was identified.

Table 1

Infrared absorption peaks [cm^{-1}] of analyzed wall pigment samples with relative intensity (s = strong, m = medium, w = weak) and tentative assignment (v = stretching vibration; δ = bending vibration)

Pigment color	Sample	IR peaks [cm^{-1}]											
		470/545	711	747-753	778	796-798	871-873	908-913	1001-1026	1244-1268	1397-1422	1646/1795	
Red	APL-1	w	w				m		s		m		
	APL-2	w	w				s		w		s		
	APL-4	w	w	w			s		s	w	s		
	APL-5	m	w	w			s		s	w	s		
	APL-6	m	w				s		w		s		
	APL-7	m	w				m	w	w	w	s		
	APL-8	w	w				m	w	w	w	s		
	APL-10	w	w				m	w	w	w	s	w	
	APL-11	w	w				s	w	s	w	s	w	
	APL-12	w	w				m	w	m	w	s	w	
	APL-13	w	w				m	w	m	w	m	w	
	APL-14	w	w				s	w	s	w	s	w	
	APL-15	w	w				s	w	s	w	s	w	
	Yellow	APL-2			w		w	w	w	s	w	w	
		APL-10			w		w	w	w	s	w	s	
APL-11			w	w	w	w	m	w	s	w	m		
APL-13			w	w	w	w	m	w	s	w	m		
Green	APL-3		w			w	s		s	w	s	w	
	APL-11		w			w	s		s	w	s	w	
Grey	APL-2		w	w	w	w	s		s	w	s	m	
	APL-6		w	w	w	w	s		s	w	s	m	
	APL-12		w	w	w	w	s		s	w	s	m	
	APL-15		w	w	w	w	s		s	w	s	m	
Black	APL-3		w	w		w	s	s		w	s	s	
	APL-4		w	w	w	w	m	w	s	w	m	s	
	APL-9		w				s		w	s	s		
	APL-4		w				s	w	w	w	s	w	
	APL-6		w				s	w	m	w	s	w	
	APL-10		w				s	w	m	w	s	w	
	APL-14		w				s	w	m	w	s	w	
	APL-15		w				s	w	m	w	s	w	
Tentative assignment		$\delta(\text{Fe-O})/$ $\nu(\text{Fe-O})$	$\delta(\text{CO}_3^{2-})$	Si-O-Al	$\nu(\text{Si-O})$	$\nu(\text{Si-O})$	$\delta(\text{CO}_3^{2-})$	Al-OH	$\nu(\text{Si-O})/$ $\nu(\text{Si-O-Al})$	$\nu(\text{C-O})$	$\nu(\text{CO}_3^{2-})$	$\nu(\text{C-C})/$ $\delta(\text{CO}_3^{2-})$	

FTIR vibrational spectra of carbonates exhibit different types of vibrations, including symmetric stretching, usually inactive in the IR, asymmetric stretching, out-of-plane bending, and in-plane bending, according to data revealed by several authors [25–27]. Generally, in pure calcite (CaCO_3), the last three vibrational bands are recorded at $\sim 1427\text{ cm}^{-1}$, 876 cm^{-1} , and 725 cm^{-1} , but the positions of these bands are slightly changed due to the presence of other mineral compounds [28, 29]. In this regard, characteristic calcite bands were found at 711 cm^{-1} (weak peaks) and $871\text{--}873\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (strong/medium peaks) both associated with CO_3^{2-} bending, as well as an intense band $1397\text{--}1422\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to stretching of CO_3^{2-} (Table 1). Instrumental artifacts for CO_2 correction explain the weak signals at wavenumbers between 2340 cm^{-1} and 2360 cm^{-1} (all spectra). Calcite is a major component of mortars and wall coatings. Apart from calcite, several silicates (kaolinite/muscovite) were found in analyzed samples. In this regard, Si–O–Al/Si–O–Si asymmetrical stretching bands were found around $1008/1026\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (strong/medium peaks) and were assigned to phyllosilicates (*i.e.*, muscovite, illite) and clay minerals, respectively. The weak peaks at 778 and $796\text{--}798\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were attributed to Si–O stretching vibration in quartz. The weak peaks (except the APL-3 sample) at $910\text{--}913\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were assigned to group Al–OH in kaolinite. Weak peaks around $1244\text{--}1268\text{ cm}^{-1}$, were assigned to C–O stretching vibrations from mineral oil. Along with Ca, C, and O (calcite), the hematite-derived Fe (pigment) was identified by micro-FTIR spectroscopy. The O–H bending of absorbed H_2O , phyllosilicates (*i.e.*, illite, muscovite), and clay minerals (*i.e.*, kaolinite) were around 1646 cm^{-1} . The weak/medium peaks at $470/545$ were assigned to Fe–O bending/Fe–O stretching vibration in hematite. The black pigment showed characteristic peaks of graphite (1646 cm^{-1}). Cinnabar, which usually produces bright red colors, was not detected in samples.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study represents the first step in archaeological analysis; several non-invasive techniques were applied to characterize the pigments from Roman wall fragments. Based on the preliminary findings of this study, the wall ancient paintings, in which mineral pigments were used, must be given special consideration in terms of the influence of indoor (or even outdoor) humidity. Further, this could provide insights into the long-term effects of ancient paintings' exposure to indoor humidity and pollutants. This study could be a breakthrough for future studies, as measurements by non-invasive techniques across heritage samples to understand the origin of wall painting designs and colors.

Acknowledgements. This research was funded by the Ministry of Research, Innovation, and Digitization [project 43PFE/30.12.2021] and by the Ministry of Education [project CNFIS-FDI-2024-F-0002].

REFERENCES

1. T.L. Martinez, O.L. Cruz, A.G. Bueno, A.I. Calero-Castillo, V.M. Florez, *Lucentum* **35**, 155–170 (2016).
2. I.C. Salvador, M. Antonia, Z. Muñoz, *Ge-Conservación* **16**, 45–61 (2019).
3. V. Guglielmi, V. Comite, M. Andreoli, F. Demartin, C.A. Lombardi, P. Fermo, *Applied Sciences* **10**(20), 7121 (2020).
4. M.L. Enríquez, *Revista de Arqueología e Antigüidade* **33**, 239–256 (2014).
5. R. Piovesan, L. Maritan, M. Amatucci, L. Nodari, J. Neguer, *European Journal of Mineralogy* **28**, 435–448 (2016).
6. E. Gliozzo, F. Cavari, D. Damiani, I. Memmi, *Archaeometry* **54**, 278–293 (2012).
7. M. Jaro, Comparison of the painting materials used for wall painting in four sites of the Roman province Pannonia, Proceedings of the International Workshop on Roman Wall Painting – Fribourg 7–9 March 1996, pp.75–84, Institute of Mineralogy and Petrography, Fribourg, 1997.
8. S. Rozenberg, Pigments and fresco fragments from Herod’s palace at Jericho, Proceedings of the International Workshop on Roman Wall Painting – Fribourg 7–9 March 1996, pp. 63–74, Institute of Mineralogy and Petrography, Fribourg, 1997.
9. I. Segal, N. Porat, Composition of pigments from the Hellenistic walls in Acre, Proceedings of the International Workshop on Roman Wall Painting – Fribourg 7–9 March 1996, pp. 85–92, Institute of Mineralogy and Petrography, Fribourg, 1997.
10. V. Meggiolaro, G.M. Molin, U. Pappalardo, P.P. Vergerio, Contribution to studies on Roman wall painting materials and techniques in Greece: Corinth, the southeast building, Proceedings of the International Workshop on Roman Wall Painting – Fribourg 7–9 March 1996, pp. 105–120, Institute of Mineralogy and Petrography, Fribourg, 1997.
11. I. Kakoulli, Roman wall paintings in Cyprus: a scientific investigation of their technology, In Proceedings of the International Workshop on Roman Wall Painting – Fribourg 7–9 March 1996, pp. 131–142, Institute of Mineralogy and Petrography, Fribourg, 1997.
12. M. Fuchs, H. Bearat, Analyses physico-chimiques et peintures murales romaines a Avenches, Bosingen, Dietikon et Vallon, Proceedings of the International Workshop on Roman Wall Painting – Fribourg 7–9 March 1996, pp. 181–192, Institute of Mineralogy and Petrography, Fribourg, 1997.
13. R. Bugini, L. Folli, Materials and making techniques of Roman Republican wall paintings, Proceedings of the International Workshop on Roman Wall Painting – Fribourg 7–9 March 1996, pp. 121–130, Institute of Mineralogy and Petrography, Fribourg, 1997.
14. M.A. Moreno, M.P. de Luxan, F. Dorrego, The conservation and scientific investigations of the wall paintings in the Roman themes, Campo Vades, Gijon, Spain, Proceedings of the International Workshop on Roman Wall Painting – Fribourg 7–9 March 1996, pp. 297–306, Institute of Mineralogy and Petrography, Fribourg, 1997.
15. A. Verone, H. Bearat, Pittori romani al lavoro. Materiali, strumenti, tecniche: evidenze archeologiche e dati analitici di un recente scavo pompeiano lungo via dell’Abbondanza, Proceedings of the International Workshop on Roman Wall Painting – Fribourg 7–9 March 1996, pp. 199–214, Institute of Mineralogy and Petrography, Fribourg, 1997.
16. R. Sidall, *Focus* **2**, 18–31 (2006).
17. M. Salvadori, C. Sbrilli, *Archaeological and Anthropological Sciences* **13**, 187 (2021).

18. A. Bintintan, M. Gligor, C. Radulescu, I.D. Dulama, R.L., R.M. Stirbescu, S. Teodorescu, I.A. Bucurica, *Analytical Letters* **52**(15), 2348–2364 (2019).
19. I.M. Cortea, L. Ghervase, O. Țentea, A.C. Pârău, R. Rădvan, *International Journal of Architectural Heritage* **14**(5), 751–761 (2019).
20. I.M. Cortea, L. Ratoiu, L. Ghervase, O. Țentea, M. Dinu, *Applied Sciences* **11**, 10049 (2021).
21. C.H. Opreanu, V.A. Lăzărescu, The province of Dacia, *Landscape Archaeology on the Northern Frontier of the Roman Empire at Porolissum. An interdisciplinary research project*, Mega Publishing House, Cluj-Napoca, 2016, pp. 49–111.
22. I. Piso, *Inscriptions d'Apulum: (Inscriptions de la Dacie Romaine – III 5)*, Mémoires de l'Académie des Inscriptions et Belles Lettres, Paris, XVI–XXI, 2001.
23. R. Ota, V. Rusu-Bolindet, D.G. Anghel, *Acta Mvsei Apvlensis* **LVII**, 149–216 (2020).
24. V. Rusu-Bolindet, The praetorium consularis from Apulum. A symbol of official power in the province of Dacia, *Proceedings of the International Conference*, Budapest, 5–6 November 2018, pp. 97–121.
25. A. Morricone, A. Macchia, L. Campanella, M. David, S. De Togni, M. Turci, A. Maras, C. Meucci, S. Ronca, *Procedia Chemistry* **8**, 231 (2013).
26. P. Sathya, G. Velraj, S. Meyvel, *Advances in Applied Science Research* **3**(2), 776 (2012).
27. A. Bintintan, M. Gligor, I.D. Dulama, C. Radulescu, C. Stihl C., R.M. Ion, S. Teodorescu, R.M. Stirbescu, I.A. Bucurica, G. Pehoiu, *Romanian Journal of Physics* **64**(5–6), 903 (2019).
28. C. Zhao, Y. Zhang, C.-C. Wang, M. Hou, A. Li, *Heritage Science*, **7** (1), 36 (2019).
29. A. Artesani, F. Di Turo, M. Zucchelli, A. Traviglia, *Coatings* **10**(3), 2020.